

DEVELOPMENTS OF HIGH DAMAGE TOLERANT, NET SHAPE COMPOSITES THROUGH TEXTILE

STRUCTURAL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper illustrates, with experimental evidence, the feasibility of the improvement of the damage resistance of composites by textile structural design. The tensile flexural and shear behavior of the 3-D braid composites were compared to laminates. A comparison was also made between 3-D braid and unidirectional reinforced metal matrix composites. The structure and properties of 3-D braid I-beams were shown to demonstrate the design possibilities with the 3-D braid textile structural preform.

INTRODUCTION

The expansion of the application of composites from secondary non-loading bearing to primary load bearing application requires a significant improvement of the damage tolerance and reliability of composites. In order to reduce the cost and broaden the usage of composites, the development of a capability for quantity production and the direct formation of structural shapes would be desirable. In order to improve the damage tolerance of composites a high level of through-thickness strength and intralaminar strength is required. The reliability of a composite depends on the uniform distribution of the materials and consistent interfacial properties. The structural integrity (handleability) of this constituent materials for the composite is critical for quantity/automated production. A method for the direct formation of the structural shapes would simplify greatly the laborious hand lay-up composite formation process.

The performance of composite structure depends on the constituent (fiber and matrix) properties, fiber-matrix interfacial characteristics, composite processing methods and variables as well as the geometric arrangement of the fibers.

Being the structural backbone of a composite, as shown in Figure 1, a wide range of textile preforms are available and they can be designed to accommodate a variety of manipulative requirements, including dimensional stability, subtle conformability and deep-draw shapeability. Woven fabrics that are essentially two-dimensional constructions exhibit good stability in the mutually orthogonal warp and fill directions. Triaxially woven

Figure 1a. Various woven and knitted fabric forms available for textile structural composites

Figure 1b. Various braided and nonwoven fabric forms available for textile structural composites

Figure 2. Basic Loom Configurations for 3-D Braiding

fabrics, made from three sets of yarns which interlace at 60° angles, offer improved isotropy and higher in-plane shear rigidity. There are also other 2-D materials in the forms of knit fabric and weft-inserted warp knit constructions. These materials offer a much wider range of form and behavior than woven fabrics. It is possible to design composites with considerable flexibility in performance, from complete directional stability to engineered directional elongation. Another emerging area in textile composites is based upon 3-D integrated structural geometry. These materials can assume complex shapes and provide a high level of transverse shear strength and impact resistance. Further improvement of the composite properties can also be made by the hybridization of fiber materials and geometry.

In this paper, the structural shape and property development of composites through textile structural design is illustrated with a specific example - the 3-D braid reinforced composites.

THE DESIGN OF 3-D BRAID REINFORCED COMPOSITES

The 3-D braiding technology is an extension of the well established 2-D braiding technology wherein the fabric is constructed by the intertwining or orthogonally interlacing of two or more yarn systems to form an integral structure. As shown by Ko [1] and Brown [2], several 3-D braiding processes have been developed in recent years. Names associated with 3-D braids are Omni Weave, Magna Weave, Matrix Braiding, Multidimensional Braid and Through-Thickness Braiding. In general, a 3-D braid can be produced in a rectangular and circular configuration as shown in Figure 2. Numerous variations of shapes can be developed from these two configurations by the proper arrangement of the starting position and the movement of the component yarns in the loom. To facilitate design, computer codes have been established in our laboratory to determine the orientation of each yarn segment in 3-D braid as well as the resulting structural shape. A computer plot of the yarns in a 3-D braid I-beam is shown in Figure 3. Basically, the orientation of a yarn segment is governed by the following relationship [3]:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{u^2 + v^2}}{w} \right)$$

where θ = yarn orientation

u = track movement (transverse direction)

v = column movement (through-thickness direction)

w = beat up sequench, or frequency of the fabric is compacted in the vertical direction.

With the knowledge of yarn type, yarn geometry and fabric geometry, the fiber volume fraction, V_f , of a 3-D braid can be determined by the following equation:

$$V_f = \frac{N_y D_y \sin(\tan^{-1}((1 + K^2)^{1/2} \tan(\theta)/K))}{A_c 9 \times 10^5 \rho \tan(\theta) (1 + K^2)^{1/2}}$$

where N_y = number of yarns; D_y = yarn linear density; θ = surface braiding angle; K = track to column ratio; A_c = cross sectional area of the composite; ρ = fiber density.

This equation can be used effectively to determine the fabric preform fabrication parameters for a given requirement of yarn orientation and fiber volume fraction.

Based on these equations for fiber orientation and fiber volume fraction of the fabric, several models have been established to represent the mechanical properties of 3-D braid reinforced composites. For example,

Yang, Ma and Chou [4] established a 'Fiber Inclination Model' based on the classical laminated plate theory. Using this model, they were able to predict the elastic properties of 3-D braid reinforced resin matrix composites. In our laboratory, we have used the following general model to predict the stress-strain behavior up to failure of a 3-D braid composite.

$$\{\epsilon\}_{xyz} = [\bar{S}] \{\sigma\}_{xyz} + \Delta T\{\alpha\}_{xyz}$$

where the compliance matrix $[\bar{S}]$ can be expressed in terms of the fiber orientation and material properties $[S]$, $[\bar{S}] = [T]^T[S][T]$.

$$[T] = \begin{pmatrix} m^2 & n^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2mn \\ n^2 & m^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2mn \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m & -n & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & n & m & 0 \\ -mn & mn & 0 & 0 & 0 & m^2 - n^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

where $m = \cos \theta$, $n = \sin \theta$. Thus, for a given stress, σ , level the corresponding strain, ϵ , can be determined numerically.

TENSILE AND FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF 3-D BRAID COMPOSITES

The tensile, flexural and short beam shear properties of graphite 3-D braid reinforced 5208 epoxy resin composites have been evaluated and detailed in a separate paper by Ko et al. [5]. As shown in Table 1, the 3-D braid composites compare favorably to the state-of-the-art laminated composites. This is especially evident when compared to the 0/90 and quasi-isotropic lay-up laminates. It should be noted that the Poisson's ratio of the braided composites reaches a level of .9 which is characteristic of braided structures. This shortcoming can be addressed, however, by proper introduction of transverse reinforcement. For example, the introduction of 10% transverse yarns, resulted in a remarkable reduction of the Poisson's ratio to a level of .27. This was accomplished with the compromise of the reduction of tensile strength and modulus to 155 ksi and 13 msi, respectively, which is still quite acceptable when compared to the 0/90 laminates.

IMPACT BEHAVIOR

The resistance of the 3-D braid resin matrix and metal matrix composite to impact loading was observed by drop weight instrumented impact test. For a glass fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite, under a 588 lb. drop weight at a velocity of 1.7 ft/s, a maximum energy of 654 ft-lb was observed. Figure 4 shows the typical time and displacement response curves for the 3-D braid glass/epoxy composites. In another test carried out on a 3-D braid Kevlar/epoxy composite, a 455 ft-lb total energy absorption was observed from an impact velocity of 17.3 ft/sec. The most interesting aspect, however, is the damage characteristics of the 3-D braid composites as shown in Figures 5A and B. It can be seen from these pictures that the integrated 3-D fabric structure limits the damage area with an intensive network of crack arrestors.

In a separate study, this impact damage resistance of unidirectional and 3-D braid fiber FP reinforced aluminum-lithium composites were compared. As shown in Table 2, at half the fiber volume fraction (17% vs. 35%), the 3-D braid reinforced composite exhibits a significantly higher level of impact resistance. The ability of the 3-D braid reinforced composite to limit

Figure 3. Computer Plot of 3-D Braided I-Beam

Figure 4.

 INSTRUMENTED IMPACT TEST

(1X1X1)E g1/Ep 5X5X 1/2

Drop weight	= 588.50lb	Data disk	DUPNT105
Top radius	= .500in	DRM scale	22.2kn/Div
Temperature	= 70.0 F	Flag grid	.040in
VO	= 8.03ft/s		
K.E.	= 589.24ft-Lb	Vf (calc)	= 1.73ft/s

Figure 5. Impact Behavior of 3-D Braid Kevlar/Epoxy Composite

Figure 6. Impact Behavior of FP/Al-Li Composites

Figure 7. Structural Shapes Produced by the 3-D Braiding Process

Figure 8. Design of 3-D Braid Composite I-Beam

TABLE 1. Mechanical Properties of Graphite/Epoxy Composites

Properties	3-D Composite		Laminated Composite
	3-D braid AS4/5208	Woven AS4/3501	Unidirectional AS4/3501
Tensile Strength (ksi)	197	200	310
Tensile Modulus (msi)	14.6	10	21.5
Flexural Strength (ksi)	149	130	260
Flexural Modulus (msi)	10.5	9.5	18.5
SBS Strength (ksi)	15.3	9	18.5
Poisson's Ratio	.90	.10	.25
Fiber Volume (%)	65	62	62

TABLE 2. Impact Properties of FP/Al-Li Composites

Fiber Volume Fraction	3-D Braid 17%	Unidirectional Tape 35%
Total Energy Absorbed (ft-lbs)	196	93.5
Crack Initiation Energy (ft-lbs)	48.9	10.5
Crack Propagation Energy (ft-lbs)	145.5	83
Maximum Load (1,000 lbs)	5.6	2.6

TABLE 3. Composite I-Beam Design Matrix

I-Beam	A	B	C	D
Matrix/Fiber	Polyester/ E-Glass	Polyester/ E-Glass	Polyester/ E-Glass/ Carbon	Polyester/ E-Glass/ Carbon
Longitudinal Lay-in	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
V_f	.5	.6	.65	.65
Carbon:Glass	0:1	0:1	1:1	1:1

TABLE 4. Flexural Properties of Composite I-Beam.

I-Beam	A	B	C	D
Tensile Modulus (msi)	2.66	4.43	6.50	9.68
Compressive Modulus (msi)	3.06	4.43	9.90	16.60
Flexural Strength (ksi)	21.80	34.50	29.30	46.60

damage area is illustrated quite clearly in the photographs shown in Figure 6.

DEVELOPMENT OF STRUCTURAL SHAPES

A wide variety of structural shapes as shown in Figure 7, have been demonstrated successfully in our laboratory by the 3-D braiding process. For the purpose of illustration, the structure and properties of a 3-D braid reinforced composite I-beam is shown herein. The formation and testing of the composite I-beam have been detailed in a separate publication [6]. Based on the computer design lay-out shown in Figure 8A, several material and geometric design variations, as illustrated in Figure 8B, were considered. Using E-glass, polyester matrix and the fiber/geometry combination outlined in Table 3, the flexural properties of the composite I-beams determined by a 3-point bending method are shown in Table 4.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated in this paper that the current need of higher level of toughness and the direct formation of structural shapes in structural composites can be addressed by textile structural design. With the availability of multidirectional, multilayer thin fabric preform and the 3-D braided thick fabric preforms, wide range of properties and structural shapes can be developed. It was shown that the integrated textile structure is especially suitable for controlling the damage area incurred by impact. By proper positioning of the yarns and the selection of fabric geometry, it has been shown that the elastic properties of the 3-D braid composites such as tensile modulus and Poisson's ratio; can be controlled. Accordingly, in addition to the types of fiber and matrix, fiber architecture can be used effectively to provide additional options in composite design.

REFERENCES

1. Ko, F.K., Three Dimensional Fabrics for Composites - An Introduction to the Magnawave Structure, p. 1609, in Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, Hayashi et al., editors, ICCM-IV, Tokyo, 1982, pp. 1609-1616.
2. Brown, R.T., Through-The-Thickness Braiding Technology, 30th National Sample Symposium, March 19-21, 1985, pp. 1509-1518.
3. Ko, F.K. and Pastore, C.P., Structure and Properties of an Integrated 3-D Fabric for Structural Composites, Recent Advances in Composites in the United States and Japan, ASTM STP 864, J.R. Vinson and M. Tayan, Eds., ASTM 1985, pp. 428-439.
4. Yang, J.M., Ma., C.L. and Chou, T.W., Fiber Inclination Model of Three-Dimensional Textile Structural Composites, to be published in the Journal of Composite Materials.
6. Ko, F.K., Tensile Strength and Modulus of a 3-D Braid Composite, 7th Symposium on Composite Materials Testing and Design, ASTM, 1984.
6. Florentine, R.A., Chou, T.W. and Ko, F., Magnetically Woven Composite I-Beam, 40th Annual Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composite Institute, The Society of the Plastics Industry, Inc., Jan. 28-Feb. 1, 1985.